

Vitamins: Antioxidant Micronutrients and the Immune Response

Fatma Mustafa Muhammad

College of Dentistry / University of Tikrit, Iraq

Chateen I. Ali Pambuk

College of Dentistry / University of Tikrit, Iraq

Abstract

The body is shielded from infections by the immune system, which acts as a firewall. A multitude of cells, glands, and other components make up the immune system, and they all function flawlessly together. Repeated exposure to bacteria, viruses, and other pathogens weakens the immune system over time. It has to be reinforced and put back in a healthy condition. For those who are severely malnourished, vitamins can help boost immunity and combat illnesses and health issues. Although vitamins and nutritional supplements can help make up for vitamin shortages, it is preferable to get these vitamins from meals since the body absorbs and uses them effectively.

By altering one's food, taking supplements to increase immunity, and changing one's lifestyle, one can enhance their immune system. The greatest and most significant vitamins that strengthen the immune system are reviewed in this article.

Introduction

A balanced diet must include vitamins. For the majority of vitamins, the amount that most healthy individuals require each day to stay healthy has been established as the recommended daily allowance (RDA). For several vitamins, the permissible upper consumption level, or safe upper limit, has been established. The chance of experiencing toxicity rises when the amount taken beyond the allowable limit [1].

Excessive consumption of some vitamins may be hazardous. Inadequate consumption of specific vitamins can result in nutritional issues. However, vitamin deficiencies are unlikely to affect people who eat a variety of foods. Deficiency in vitamin D is an exception. Certain groups, such as older adults, are more susceptible to vitamin D deficiency even if they eat a diverse diet. Other vitamin deficiencies may develop in people who consume a restricted diet that does not contain adequate amounts of a particular vitamin. For example, vegetarians who avoid all animal products may not be getting enough vitamin B12, which is found in animal products. While, People at high risk for vitamin deficiencies (such as those who have undergone bariatric surgery, are on dialysis, or have an

alcohol use disorder) may benefit from taking daily multivitamins, even if biotin or pantothenic acid (B vitamins) are nearly never inadequate. Strengthening the immune system is crucial for maintaining the body's health and defending it against infections and poisons, particularly in the winter when diseases are more common [1-3].

The human body's immune system is said to be the first line of defense for its safety and well-being. With the current state of anxiety and panic around the spread of the coronavirus and preventing infection, people are thinking more about ways to boost and strengthen immunity in the body through a variety of foods that include essential vitamins or other components that the body cannot function without. This can lower the incidence of illnesses at any time. Eating a variety of foods and maintaining a balanced diet are essential in our efforts to boost our immune systems because they prepare the body to withstand the attacks of bacteria, viruses, and toxins [2,4-6].

The following list of vitamins and minerals can boost the immune system's immunity, hence nutrition experts recommend boosting the immune system

More Information

How to cite this article: Muhammad FM, Ali Pambuk CI. Vitamins: Antioxidant Micronutrients and the Immune Response. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):111-5.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmr.2024.2(6).14

Keywords:

Vitamins,
antioxidant,
micronutrients,
immune response.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

through diet rather than using pharmaceuticals and treatments.

Vitamin C

One of the most important nutrients for the human body is vitamin C, also referred to as ascorbic acid. Like carbohydrates, it dissolves in water and is essential for the body to produce collagen. It is a crucial protein for the development of connective tissue and the promotion of wound healing. The human body has to get vitamin C from meals high in it or from nutritional supplements because it cannot manufacture it on its own.

It is well recognized for its ability to strengthen the immune system; as an antioxidant, it combats dangerous free radicals in the body, perhaps lowering or delaying the onset of several illnesses. In addition to helping white blood cells do their jobs better by shielding them from potentially dangerous substances like free radicals, vitamin C also aids in the development of white blood cells called lymphocytes and phagocytes, which help the body fight off infections [7-9]. Vitamin C's advantages Vitamin C has several health advantages, the most notable of which are:

Lowering the chance of developing chronic illnesses

Because it helps shield cells from dangerous chemicals called free radicals, which build up in the body and cause oxidative stress, a condition linked to several chronic illnesses, vitamin C is a potent antioxidant that can boost the body's immune system. Consequently, vitamin C contributes to a 30% rise in blood antioxidant levels, strengthening the body's defenses against inflammation [8,10].

Lowering the chance of developing heart disease

Numerous variables raise the risk of heart disease, including high blood pressure, high levels of bad cholesterol, and low levels of good cholesterol. Vitamin C may help lower these risk factors and, consequently, lower the risk of heart disease.

Aid in preventing iron deficiency in the body Since iron is essential for the production of red blood cells and the movement of oxygen throughout the body, vitamin C supplements can enhance the body's ability to absorb iron from food, lowering the risk of anemia in those who are susceptible to iron shortage [1,9,11].

Boosting immunity in the body

The development of white blood cells, which help the body fight off illness, is stimulated by vitamin C, which also makes the cells more efficient and shields them from damage caused by dangerous chemicals called free radicals. Preserving memory as we age According to studies, oxidative stress and inflammation around the brain, spine, and nerves can raise the risk of dementia. As a strong antioxidant, vitamin C helps lower these inflammations, which has been demonstrated to have a protective effect on memory and cognitive function as people age [8,9,12].

Vitamin A

The term "vitamin" A refers to a class of unsaturated chemical compounds that are fat-soluble and play several essential roles in the human body. This fatty vitamin is kept in reserve in the liver.

Retinol, sometimes known as "vitamin A," can be found in animal sources as retinyl palmitate, an ester that the small intestine breaks down into retinol. Provitamin A, which is found in various fruits and vegetables, is made up of carotenoids, such as beta-carotene and alpha-carotene together [2,13].

A genetic mutation that decreases the body's capacity to convert carotenoids into "vitamin A" is thought to affect 45% of the population. Carotenoids are present in fruits and vegetables and are converted by the body into two molecules of retinol (alcohol), the body's active form of vitamin A. Vitamin A Because of its antioxidant qualities, vitamin A can help shield cells from the damaging effects of free radicals, which can lead to a number of illnesses. Additionally, vitamin A is well-known for its anti-inflammatory qualities, which support immune system performance. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in controlling hormonal immune processes and cellular immunological responses. Consuming vitamin A has decreased the prevalence of several infectious disorders [1,13,14].

"Vitamin A" comes from a variety of sources, including: Sources of animals: High levels of "Vitamin A" may be found in liver and beef. Liver of lamb. Liver oil from cod. Butter and cheese. eggs, salmon, tuna, and seafood.

Sources of plants: Vegetables: Provitamin A-rich vegetables include red peppers, spinach, lettuce, potatoes, turnips, carrots, and green turnips.

The significance of the vitamin

Vision Following its conversion from retinol (alcohol) to retinal (aldehyde), the latter joins forces with the opsin protein to generate iodopsin in the retina's cone cells and rhodopsin in its rod cells. These substances are crucial for both color vision and low-light perception .

Maintenance of skin cells: By triggering the genes that change immature skin cells into mature skin cells, retinoic acid preserves the integrity of skin cells [2,4].

As an antioxidant, it shields cells from harm brought on by chemicals known as free radicals. These radicals are thought to be connected to aging in addition to being detrimental to cells.

Prevention of age-related macular degeneration: According to a big clinical research, taking a certain vitamin combination that included beta-carotene reduced the chance of acquiring age-related macular degeneration by 25% in persons who were at high risk of getting the condition [14,15].

More research is needed on cancer prevention, particularly with regard to prostate, lung, and other cancers.

Reducing cholesterol: The body contains cholesterol, which is a waxy, fat-like material. Cholesterol is essential for the body's correct operation since it forms the backbone of cell membranes and aids in the production of hormones. On the other hand, excessive cholesterol buildup can cause the blood arteries to constrict and stiffen, raising the risk of heart disease. Although further clinical research is needed to confirm this, research has indicated that consuming adequate "vitamin A" in the diet may naturally help decrease blood cholesterol levels to promote heart health [5,13].

Encourage tissue repair: Vitamin A is necessary for good skin and can aid in the healing of wounds, so it's critical to consume enough of it in your diet.

The significance of vitamin A for the immune system in individuals with coronavirus infections.

The immune system depends on vitamin A, and a lack of it increases the body's vulnerability to infection, particularly in the respiratory system, which includes the lungs, sinuses, and throat, since it is vital for the production of mucin, or mucus, a crucial component of the mucus membrane. The lymphatic system layer and the epithelial layer are also impacted by vitamin A. These two serve as a barrier against microorganisms [6,14,15].

Your body activates phagocytes in response to pathogens (bacteria, viruses, etc.) entering the body. The pathogens are eaten by these big phagocytes. The thymus gland, which is situated directly above the heart, uses phagocytes to instruct immune cells and serve as the body's first line of defense against infection. In fact, vitamin A may be activated or synthesized by the thymus gland. Being a stored vitamin, too much vitamin A can lead to disease. Supplements and skin treatments that include retinal generate this dangerous excess, not natural sources.

Vitamin D

In addition to helping the body absorb calcium, the mineral that is responsible for the healthy development of teeth and bones, and for maintaining proper levels of calcium and phosphorus in the blood, vitamin D is one of the most essential nutrients needed to build the immune system since it can lower the risk of colds and the flu. It is important to note that vitamin D is known as the sunshine vitamin since it is produced by the skin upon exposure to the sun's UV radiation.

White blood cells, one of the body's most vital defenses against infection, are improved and inflammation is decreased by vitamin D. Additionally, it supports a quick immunological response, which boosts and accelerates healings [3,16].

An elevated risk of upper respiratory infections, including influenza and allergic asthma, is linked to low vitamin D levels. Vitamin D supplementation strengthens the body's defenses against respiratory infections [7].

A 2019 study conducted at Queen Mary University in the United Kingdom found that individuals who were already vitamin D deficient had a lower risk of respiratory infections when they took vitamin D supplements. Vitamin D may greatly strengthen and increase the immune system, which speeds up recovery from COVID-19 [17].

Vitamin D comes in two forms that are necessary for proper nutrition:

Yeast protozoa and plants both synthesize vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol). High-dose supplements often employ this form.

Cholecalciferol, or vitamin D₃, is the most potent form of the vitamin. When the skin is exposed to direct sunlight, it forms. The most popular dietary source of this vitamin is fortified foods, particularly dairy and grains. Additionally, fatty fish, liver, egg yolks, and fish liver oils contain vitamin D₃ [4,18].

In fact the liver is where most vitamin D is kept. The body does not use vitamin D₂ or D₃. As a result, the liver and kidneys must process (metabolize) both forms to produce the active form, either calcitriol or vitamin D. The intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphorus is improved by this active form. Mineralization is the process by which calcium and phosphorus bond with bones to improve their density and strength. Thus, calcitriol is necessary for bone growth, development, and healing [19].

Vitamin E

Tocopherol, often known as vitamin E, is categorized as an antioxidant because it participates in chemical processes within cells and shields them from harm produced by free radicals, which are byproducts of regular cell activity. Damage may result from some of these interactions [2].

As a fat-soluble vitamin, vitamin E dissolves in fat and is better absorbed when taken with fat, just as vitamins A, K, and D. Wheat germ, green leafy vegetables, nuts, seeds, and vegetable oils are all excellent providers of vitamin E [2,7].

Little vitamin E penetrates the placenta, therefore newborns have comparatively low stores of it. Vitamin E insufficiency is more common in newborns, particularly preterm babies. However, as infants age, this danger often diminishes because babies receive adequate vitamin E from formula or breast milk. Adults can lower their risk of vitamin E insufficiency by storing substantial levels of the vitamin in fatty tissue [4,20].

Vitamin E is a potent antioxidant that aids in the body's defense against illness and infection. One of the most significant biochemical processes that contributes to the body's immune system's power is this vitamin. It is crucial for healing damaged bodily tissues and avoiding cardiovascular disease and cancer. When the body lacks it, red blood cells are destroyed and nerves are damaged. Both men and women become infertile as a

result of it. Nuts, legumes, green vegetables, vegetable oils, and whole grains are the main sources of this vitamin [1,7,21].

Summary

The immune system serves as the primary defense mechanism that safeguards the body against external threats and harmful pathogens. Maintaining the strength of this system, often referred to as a defense mechanism, is crucial in minimizing the risk of infections and diseases. To ensure the immune system operates effectively, it is beneficial to incorporate immune-enhancing foods alongside a nutritious diet. Fortifying the immune system is essential for protecting the body from potential illnesses and harmful microorganisms. Currently, there is no definitive test to assess the strength of this system. Therefore, it is advisable to engage in regular physical activity in conjunction with adhering to a balanced and healthy diet whenever feasible.

The consumption of supplements that include vitamins, minerals, and various other compounds, when deemed necessary, can enhance the immune response and safeguard the body against potential illnesses. Below are several supplements that may be beneficial in bolstering the immune system.

Vitamin C: This vitamin is crucial for maintaining a healthy immune system. It serves to shield the body from a range of infections and diseases. Vitamin C enhances various immune functions and establishes a protective barrier against infections. Furthermore, it contributes to sustaining robust immunity by facilitating cell regeneration.

Vitamin D: This compound is essential for both immune function and bone health. Vitamin D amplifies the pathogen-fighting capabilities of monocytes and macrophages, which are vital components of the immune system and are classified as white blood cells. It also promotes an improved immune response by mitigating inflammation.

Vitamin E: Recognized as a potent antioxidant, vitamin E protects the body from infections and aids in combating them. Research indicates that vitamin E is among the most effective nutrients for supporting immune function.

References

- [1] Elmadfa I, Meyer AL. The role of the status of selected micronutrients in shaping the immune function. *Endocr Metab Immune Disord Drug Targets*. 2019 Dec 1;19(8):1100-15.
- [2] Thurnham DI. Micronutrients and immune function: some recent developments. *J Clin Pathol*. 1997 Nov 1;50(11):887-91.
- [3] Alpert PT. The role of vitamins and minerals on the immune system. *Home Health Care Manag Pract*. 2017 Aug;29(3):199-202.
- [4] Gombart AF, Pierre A, Maggini S. A review of micronutrients and the immune system: working in harmony to reduce the risk of infection. *Nutrients*. 2020 Jan 16;12(1):236. doi:10.3390/nu12010236.
- [5] Maggini S, Pierre A, Calder PC. Immune function and micronutrient requirements change over the life course. *Nutrients*. 2018;10(10):1531. doi:10.3390/nu10101531.
- [6] Micronutrient Information Center. Immunity in depth. Linus Pauling Institute [Internet]. 2016. Available from: <http://lpi.oregonstate.edu/mic/health-disease/immunity>
- [7] Maggini S, Beveridge S, Sorbara JP, Senatore G. Feeding the immune system: the role of micronutrients in restoring resistance to infections. *CAB Rev*. 2008;3(1):1-21.
- [8] Jafari D, Esmailzadeh A, Mohammadi-Kordkhalay M, Rezaei N. Vitamin C and the immune system. In: *Nutrition and immunity*. 2019:81-102.
- [9] Carr AC, Maggini S. Vitamin C and immune function. *Nutrients*. 2017 Nov;9(11):1211. doi:10.3390/nu9111211.
- [10] Hemilä H, Chalker E. Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;1:CD000980.
- [11] Moreira A, Kekkonen RA, Delgado L, Fonseca J, Korpela R, Haahtela T. Nutritional modulation of exercise-induced immunodepression in athletes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur J Clin Nutr*. 2007;61(4):443-60. doi:10.1038/sj.ejcn.1602546.
- [12] Hemilä H, Louhiala P. Vitamin C for preventing and treating pneumonia. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013;CD005532.
- [13] Gürbüz M, Aktaş Ş. Understanding the role of vitamin A and its precursors in the immune system. *Nutr Clin Métab*. 2022 May 1;36(2):89-98.
- [14] Roy S, Awasthi A. Vitamin A and the immune system. In: *Nutrition and immunity*. 2019:53-73.
- [15] Huang Z, Liu Y, Qi G, Brand D, Zheng SG. Role of vitamin A in the immune system. *J Clin Med*. 2018 Sep;7(9):258. doi:10.3390/jcm7090258.
- [16] Aranow C. Vitamin D and the immune system. *J Investig Med*. 2011 Aug;59(6):881-6. doi:10.231/JIM.0b013e31821b8755.
- [17] Bae M, Kim H. The role of vitamin C, vitamin D, and selenium in immune system against COVID-19. *Molecules*. 2020 Nov 16;25(22):5346. doi:10.3390/molecules25225346.
- [18] Wessels I, Rink L. Micronutrients in autoimmune diseases: possible therapeutic benefits of zinc and vitamin D. *J Nutr Biochem*. 2020 Mar;77:108240. doi:10.1016/j.jnutbio.2019.108240.

[19] Sassi F, Tamone C, D'Amelio P. Vitamin D: nutrient, hormone, and immunomodulator. *Nutrients*. 2018 Nov 3;10(11):1656. doi:10.3390/nu10111656.

[20] Lee GY, Han SN. The role of vitamin E in immunity. *Nutrients*. 2018 Nov 1;10(11):1614. doi:10.3390/nu10111614.

[21] Noor S, Piscopo S, Gasmi A. Nutrients interaction with the immune system. *Arch Razi Inst*. 2021 Dec;76(6):1579-91.